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ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION ASSOCIATED WITH SHEEHAN SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Sheehan syndrome, a rare but serious postpartum condition, results from ischemic damage to the anterior pituitary gland caused by significant bleeding during or after childbirth. This damage leads to varying levels of pituitary hormone deficiencies, with symptoms ranging from lactation failure and amenorrhea to hypothyroidism and adrenal insufficiency, which can appear immediately after delivery or much later. Anxiety is increasingly noted as a significant comorbidity in Sheehan syndrome. The chronic hormonal deficits, especially of cortisol and thyroid hormones, are linked to neuropsychiatric symptoms, including anxiety. Secondary adrenal insufficiency leads to reduced cortisol levels, impairing the stress response and potentially heightening anxiety. Similarly, hypothyroidism affects mood and cognitive functions, further complicating mental health. Diagnosing Sheehan syndrome relies on clinical history, particularly obstetric hemorrhage, and pituitary hormone tests, with MRI scans often showing an empty sella or other pituitary abnormalities. Treatment involves lifelong hormone replacement tailored to specific deficiencies, including glucocorticoids, thyroid hormones, sex steroids, and sometimes growth hormone. Managing anxiety in these patients necessitates a multidisciplinary approach, incorporating psychological support, counseling, and potentially medications such as anxiolytics or antidepressants. Ensuring optimal hormone replacement is crucial, as it can help alleviate neuropsychiatric symptoms. In summary, Sheehan syndrome presents complex endocrine and psychiatric challenges. Early diagnosis and a comprehensive treatment plan addressing both hormonal and mental health aspects are essential for improving the quality of life for affected women.

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INTRODUCTION

Sheehan syndrome, or postpartum hypopituitarism, emerges from severe postpartum haemorrhage, posing a rare yet significant threat. It entails pituitary gland impairment due to inadequate blood supply, culminating in hormonal deficits.^[1] Sheehan syndrome mainly results from severe postpartum haemorrhage, leading to reduced blood flow and ischemic necrosis in the pituitary gland. Factors such as insufficient obstetric care, existing pituitary conditions, prolonged low blood pressure, coagulation disorders like DIC, and placental abruption further increase bleeding risks during childbirth, raising the chances of pituitary ischemia and Sheehan syndrome.^[2] Persistent hypotension diminishes pituitary blood supply, fostering tissue damage and necrosis, especially in the anterior pituitary. This cascade yields shortages in vital hormones—ACTH, TSH, LH, FSH, GH, and prolactin—culminating in clinical symptoms like adrenal insufficiency, hypothyroidism, hypogonadism, growth hormone deficiency, and lactation impairment.^[3] Diagnosing Sheehan syndrome involves a multifaceted approach. Clinical evaluation entails gathering obstetric history and assessing for symptoms like fatigue, weakness, and hormonal irregularities. Hormonal testing measures levels of various hormones, including ACTH, TSH, LH, FSH, GH, and cortisol, often requiring dynamic testing for confirmation. Imaging studies like MRI examine pituitary structure, typically revealing empty sella syndrome. Stimulation tests assess pituitary function, such as adrenal and thyroid activity. Additional investigations may be necessary based on clinical presentation, including evaluations for secondary adrenal insufficiency and associated conditions like diabetes insipidus, ensuring comprehensive diagnosis and management.^[4] Sheehan syndrome is thought to originate from hypotension triggered by postpartum hemorrhage. Risk increases in individuals with predisposing factors such as pituitary gland enlargement during pregnancy, small sellaturcica, vasospasm, and a thrombophilic condition.^[5]

Case presentation:

A 36-year-old female patient brought to the gynaecology 1 year after delivery with chief complaints of weakness, extreme fatigue, difficulties with breast feeding, unable to do daily chores, fearfulness, undue suspicion. She was irritable and in addition, she had begun to neglect her daily chores and her functions as a mother. The symptoms had present for 8 months and worsened over 1 month.

She was mother of two children her last pregnancy was complicated with hypothyroidism. Childbirth by vaginal delivery was complicated with heavy bleeding and experienced difficulty in lactating her child and did not experience any menstrual bleeding since child birth.

She was 58kg and height of 152cm, she had tachycardia (heart rate of 90bpm) with a blood pressure of 130/80mmhg. The rest of the physical examination was normal.

Her orientation with regard to time, day, month, place, and city was normal. Her short-term and longterm memory as well as other aspects of extended cognitive assessment was normal. Her mental state examination revealed an anxious mood with fleeting passive suicidal ideas and depression.

Initial laboratory investigations showed hyponatraemia, elevated creatine phosphokinase and elevated TSH and free low T4 and was already on levothyroxine.

She was referred to psychiatry and endocrinology for further evaluation and management. With a 9am cortisol of 221 nmol/L, she was started on levothyroxine under the cover of hydrocortisone. A diagnosis of panhypopituitarism was made. Levothyroxine and hydrocortisone were continued. Symptoms, including psychotic symptoms and hyponatraemia, improved remarkably within two weeks and risperidone was discontinued. Oestrogen and progesterone replacement therapy was initiated later.

DISCUSSION

Our patient initially presented with weakness, extreme fatigue, fearfulness, and undue suspicion, suggesting an organic pathology with hypothyroid features. Timely endocrine referral confirmed the diagnosis and initiated specific treatment, resulting in significant clinical improvement. Additionally, she exhibited symptoms of anxiety, including restlessness, palpitations, and excessive worry, along with depressive symptoms such as low mood, anhedonia, and social withdrawal. Psychiatric evaluation identified moderate anxiety and depressive disorders, necessitating intervention alongside hormonal replacement therapy. The diagnosis of Sheehan syndrome was established based on the temporal relationship of symptoms to childbirth, a history indicative of postpartum hemorrhage, and characteristic anterior pituitary dysfunction. Notably, low prolactin levels leading to lactation failure are typical features of Sheehan syndrome, distinguishing it from other causes of hypopituitarism where prolactin levels are usually normal or elevated, such as lymphocytic hypophysitis.^[5]

Hormonal imbalances in Sheehan syndrome are associated with psychiatric symptoms like anxiety and depression. Hypothyroidism, a common consequence of Sheehan syndrome, can affect mood due to thyroid hormone deficiency. Similarly, adrenal insufficiency, resulting from cortisol deficiency, can exacerbate anxiety symptoms, given cortisol's role in stress regulation. Postpartum hormonal fluctuations, combined with existing hormonal deficits, increase susceptibility to mood disorders. Effective management necessitates a multidisciplinary approach, integrating hormonal replacement therapy, psychotherapy, and pharmacotherapy. Hormonal replacement aims to restore physiological hormone levels, thereby alleviating mood symptoms. Psychotherapy offers coping strategies and addresses underlying psychological distress. Additionally, psychosis can arise as a complication of severe hormonal imbalances in Sheehan syndrome, especially in cases with profound deficiencies in cortisol or thyroid hormones. Cortisol deficiency disrupts neurological function, potentially precipitating psychotic symptoms, while thyroid hormone deficiency contributes to cognitive impairment and psychosis. Prompt diagnosis and management of hormonal deficiencies are essential to mitigate the risk of psychosis and improve outcomes in individuals with Sheehan syndrome.^{[6],[7]}

Many questions remain unanswered regarding psychotic manifestations in individuals with Sheehan syndrome. One such question concerns the prolonged interval between symptom onset and the development of hormone deficiencies in certain patients, which remains unclear. Additionally, it's intriguing to explore whether specific predisposing factors contribute to psychiatric manifestations in these patients, especially when compared to a larger population of Sheehan syndrome patients without psychotic symptoms. Delving into patients' personality traits and external triggers could provide valuable insights into uncovering these answers.

CONCLUSION

Sheehan syndrome can be complicated by anxiety and depression secondary to hormonal deficiencies. Recognition and management of psychiatric symptoms are integral components of comprehensive care for individuals with Sheehan syndrome.

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